

Analysis of Volatile Organic Compounds from *Trogoderma Variabile* Ballion (Coleoptera: Dermestidae) Infested and Non-Infested Stored Grain Using SPME Coupled with GC-MS and FID

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Suggested Citation

Al-Shuwaili, T., Mahdi, S.A., & Baqir, H.A. (2024). Analysis of Volatile Organic Compounds from *Trogoderma Variabile* Ballion (Coleoptera: Dermestidae) Infested and Non-Infested Stored Grain Using SPME Coupled with GC-MS and FID. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 959-968.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).85](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).85)

Abstract:

The study seeks to employ gas chromatography combined with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) to examine the chemical profile of *Trogoderma variabile* across different host grains, including oats, wheat, and barley. It also seeks to compare samples of healthy grain (non-insect-contaminated) to those infested by *T. variabile*, to determine if unique compounds can be used to detect infestation. This would suggest that HS-SPME coupled with GC-MS could serve as a method for identifying *T. variabile* infestations. *T. variabile* was reared on the three various commodities. Solid-phase microextraction (SPME) was employed, followed by gas flame ionization (GC-FID) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) for the collection, separation, and identification of compounds. The

findings revealed that 23 compounds were identified from adult insects reared on canola and wheat.

Additionally, 26 compounds were emitted from both non-infested and infested wheat, with 22 being highly significant. Furthermore, 21 compounds showed significant differences between non-infested and infested oats. For infested and non-infested barley, 18 compounds differed significantly between the treatments.

Keywords: *Trogoderma variabile*, SPME-GC/MS, SPME-GC/FID, VOCs.

Introduction

Food supply is an urgent global issue due to fast-paced population growth and farmland deterioration (Boserup, 2011). The world's population obtains most of its daily energy needs

from grains. The total value of exported agriculture products from Australia reached \$66 billion; grain represents 31% of agriculture exported products (Jackson et. Al., 2018). Therefore, storing these grains without any losses is very important to feed the ever-growing

global population. Grain and food products can be attacked by pests such as insects, mites, and microorganisms during storage, resulting in post-harvest losses of approximately 10-15% worldwide annually (Rajendran, 2005). Infestation of stored grain by insects encourages the growth of fungi, including those that produce mycotoxins that can cause toxicity issues in humans and livestock (Freeman, 1976). Grain storage insects also decrease the quantity and quality of grain through consumption, contamination and by producing conditions ideal for microbial growth (Neethirajan et. al., 2007).

Detecting stored grain insects in large quantities of grain can be difficult, particularly at low infestation rates. Many detection methods used in stored products are often impractical due to their high cost and low sensitivity. (Neethirajan et. al., 2007). It is critical to have a robust detection system for insect infestations in stored grain to ensure healthy food for consumers and to provide an early warning system for control mitigation implementation. Detection systems also help evaluate the efficiency of pesticide treatments. Sunthilkumar et. al. (2012) showed that identifying the VOCs released by insects can be used to detect insects in stored grain. Also, volatile organic compounds (VOCs) can be used to differentiate insects, mites, and fungal species and to determine the ongoing spoilage and the causes of spoilage as each species produces unique volatile organic compounds to communicate with their species or as metabolites (Sunthilkumar et. al. 2012). Abuelnnor et al. (2010) identified unique volatile compounds from wheat flour and wheat grain infested with *T. confusum* and *S. granaries*, which were useful for early infestation monitoring.

Some other studies showed that it is the best way to monitor insect damage in stored wheat (Seitz and Ram, 2004). The headspace method for measuring volatiles has been used extensively in environmental studies and has had a significant presence in food and flavor industries for analyzing the aroma of orange juice, fresh tomato juice, and volatile compounds from grains, fermented dairy products, identifying lipid oxidation in foods and to assess the quality

of cooked beef (Oliveria et. al., 2010; Ram et. al., 1999).

In recent years, headspace solid-phase microextraction (HS-SPME) combined with gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) has been increasingly used to analyze volatile compounds from stored product insects in grain. This technique has been widely applied for the identification of VOCs in stored grain, as well as for detecting pheromones and other volatile metabolites produced by insects such as the lesser grain borer (*Rhyzopertha dominica*) and *Tribolium castaneum*. SPME GC-MS has also been used to identify spoilage by detecting species-specific VOCs produced by insects for communication. However, no detailed study has yet examined the VOCs emitted from grains infested with *Trogoderma variabile*. Modern methods applied to stored food grains could offer a rapid and efficient way to detect both internal and external infestations, even at low densities, with minimal material destruction, enabling timely pest management interventions.

In the current study, VOC profiles of *T. variabile* infested non-infested grains, including wheat, oats, and barley, were compared to determine the differences between treated plants and used as identification tools for the infestation. The goal of this study was to screen samples of healthy grain (non-insect-contaminated) compare them to the infested by *T. variabile* to establish if there are unique compounds that can be used to detect the infestation by *T. variabile*, which would indicate that HS-SPME coupled with GC-MS could be used as a way for identifying the infestation of *T. variabile*.

Materials and Methods

Grain Pre-Treatment

Fresh organic wheat, oats, and barley provided by Post-Harvest Plant Biosecurity laboratories, College of Environmental and Life Sciences, Murdoch University, Western Australia. The grain samples were placed in sealed glass jars (4 L) and put in a freezer at -20°C for 1 week to ensure they were free of live insects. The grains were then stored at 4°C until use.

Preparation of Samples for Analysis

T. variabile was obtained from the Post-Harvest Plant Biosecurity laboratories, Harry Butler Institute, Murdoch University, Western Australia. To obtain *T. variabile* adults, around 45 adults (mix between females and males) were added into 50 ml glass jars containing 15 g of wheat, oat and barley grains separately and covered with a meshed lid. The insects were reared in a controlled temperature room set at $29\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $70\pm 2\%$ relative humidity for two weeks.

Apparatus and Equipment

In this study, a solid-phase microextraction (SPME) fiber made of Divinyl benzene/carboxen/polydimethylsiloxane (DVB/CAR/PDMS) with dimensions of 50/30 μm (Sigma-Aldrich Australia, catalog number 57299-U) was utilized to capture volatile organic compounds (VOCs). An Agilent Technologies gas chromatograph model 7829A (serial number CN14272038) with a non-polar HP-5MS column (30 m \times 0.25 mm, 0.25 μm film thickness) and a flame ionization detector (FID) was used for analysis. The GC-FID conditions were as follows: the injector port temperature was maintained at 250°C , the initial oven temperature was 60°C , which increased to 250°C at a rate of 5°C per minute. The column flow rate was set at 1.1 ml/min, with a splitless mode of 20 ml/min for the first 1.5 minutes. The total runtime for the GC-FID analysis was 46 minutes.

To identify VOCs in healthy and infested grain, an Agilent GC-MS 7820A equipped with a DB-35ms column (30 m \times 250 μm \times 0.25 μm) and an MS detector 5977E (Agilent Technologies, USA) was utilized.

To obtain the VOCs, 15 grams of infested or non-infested grain were transferred to 55 ml glass vials with screw-tight caps with septa. These were incubated as described above for 72 hours before VOCs were collected from the non-infested and infested grains by SPME. The same conditions of the extraction and analysis were applied to GC-MS for the identification of grain compounds only. Five experimental replicates per treatment were taken during the

process of VOCs analysis and during the identification of VOC peaks.

Statistical Analysis

The Automatic Mass Spectral Deconvolution and Identification System (AMDIS-32) software, along with the NIST 2.2 mass spectra library, was used to identify the chemical compounds released from both non-infested and *Trogoderma variabile*-infested grains. All peak area analyses were conducted using MetaboAnalyst version 4.0 online software to calculate P-values, false discovery rates (FDR), and perform sparse Partial Least Squares-Discriminant Analysis (sPLS-DA). Samples were uploaded as columns (unpaired), with data filtering based on the mean intensity value. No normalization, data transformation, or data scaling was applied.

" Differences in results were compared using the T-test ($P\leq 0.05$) to determine the means between non-infested and infested grains. The peak area from GC-FID for each compound was divided by 100,000 for easier calculation.

Results and Discussion

Volatile Organic Compounds from Non-Infested and Infested Grains (Wheat, Oats and Barley)

A total of 26 compounds emitted from non-infested and infested wheat (Table 1); 22 compounds of VOCs were highly significant in peak area included pentanoic acid; nonanal; 5-dodecene,(Z)-; dodecane; decanal; undecane, 2,6-dimethyl-; cyclopropane, nonyl-; dodecane, 2,6,11-trimethyl-; tridecane; tridecane, 2-methyl-; 1-tetradecene; tetradecane; decane, 1-iodo-; 1-decanol, 2-hexyl-; pentadecane; tetradecanoic acid; 2-heptadecanone; oleic acid; eicosanoic acid; 11-methyltricosane; pentacosane and 11-methylpentacosane. In addition, score plots from Sparse Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (sPLS-DA) were used to determine any variables by calculating a regression for peak areas or compound concentrations. sPLS-DA was performed to show the separation of the two samples using the significant ($P<0.05$)

difference and the relationship between the VOCs from infested and non-infested wheat (Figure 1a).

There were 21 compounds with highly significant differences between non-infested and infested oats, these included cis-3-methylcyclohexanol; nonanal; decanal; undecane, 2,6-dimethyl-; pentadecane, 7-methyl-; dodecane, 2,6,11-trimethyl-; tridecane; tetradecane; 1-decanol, 2-hexyl-; pentadecane; hexadecane; 2-pentadecanone; 2-heptenoic acid, 2-ethylhexyl ester; pentadecanal-; tetradecanoic acid; 2-pentadecanone, 6,10,14-trimethyl-; pentadecanoic acid; 2-heptadecanone; n-hexadecanoic acid; octadecanoic acid and eicosanoic acid (Table 2). The average of the peak areas was analysed using sPLS-DA. The result shows the scores plot between the selected PCs (Fig. 1b). The model showed a good separation among the tested treatment groups in this experiment.

For non-infested and infested barley, 18 compounds differed significantly between the treatments (Table 3) these included nonanal; dodecane; decanal; cyclopropane, nonyl; dodecane, 2,6,11-trimethyl-; tridecane; dodecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-; 1-tetradecene; tetradecane; caryophyllene; 2-tridecanone; pentadecane; hexadecane; 2-pentadecanone; 2-pentadecanone, 6,10,14-trimethyl-; 2-heptadecanone and n-hexadecanoic acid. The result in Fig (1c) There was a good separation between non-infested and infested barley (Figure 1c).

In general, for all the grains used in this study. However, most of the compounds increased in the grain following infestation by *T. variable*. This study found that different volatiles are produced in different non-infested and infested grain samples. However, some of these compounds were detected in all grains. This agrees with Hougen et al. (Villaverde et. al., 2007), who reported that different species and varieties of cereal grains appear to produce mostly the same volatile components but in different characteristics and relative amounts. In the present study, there were differences in the number and height of the peaks emitted from

the different grains. Seitz (Seitz, 1995) investigated the volatile compounds of five cultivars of wheat grain harvested in Kansas in 1992 and 1993 and reported that amounts of some volatile compounds differed among locations and cultivars, but none of the differences appeared to be associated with intrinsic properties of the cultivars themselves. The addition of the attractive food volatiles nonanal aggregation pheromones enhanced the response by mixed-sex grain beetles, *Oryzaephilus Mercator* (Fauvel), to the pheromones (Pierce et. al., 1990).

Figure 1. Score Plots from Sparse Partial Least Squares - Discriminant Analysis (sPLS-DA) Analysis Based on Total Peak Area Obtained from GC-FID Data of Non-Infested and Adult *T. variable* Infested Grain Samples a: Wheat, b: Oats, c: Barley

Previous studies have highlighted that the feeding activity of insect species significantly influences the volatile profiles of rice grains, either enhancing or diminishing the emission of

specific VOCs. These changes in VOC emission can be closely associated with the particular pest species present (Giunts et. al., 2018).

Table 1. Significant Compounds Peak Area (One Unit Corresponds to a 10⁵ Area) Detected from Non-Infested and Adult *T. variabile* Infested Wheat Grain

Compounds	RT	NIST RI	Calculated RI	Non-infested	Infested	p value (10 ⁻³)	FDR
pentanoic acid	9.186	903	937.9	457.13±16.35	n.d.	10.598	0.00003
nonanal	12.043	1104	1063.4	1.76±0.93	24.83±8.59	3.4746	0.0010
5-dodecene, (Z)-	14.719	1176	1183.1	49.971±11.06	n.d.	4.568	0.0001
dodecane	14.953	1214	1193.7	0.3987±0.11	38.98±17.5	2.9395	0.0027
decanal	15.185	1206	1202.6	n.d.	54.18±24.7	2.7902	0.0035
undecane, 2,6-dimethyl-	15.376	1210	1210.2	0.36±0.11	1.434±0.32	3.9139	0.0004
cyclopropane, nonyl-	16.151	1285	1235.7	0.86±0.38	70.46±14.3	5.3282	0.0004
dodecane, 2,6,11-trimethyl-	17.279	1275	1273.6	n.d.	15.64±4.30	3.9261	0.0004
tridecane	17.825	1300	1293	5.1925±2.79	118.6±5.66	4.2678	0.0002
tridecane, 2-methyl-	18.548	1364	1318.2	2.7410±0.78	8.023±4.33	1.5528	0.0346
1-tetradecene	20.287	1392	1386.6	5.9900±2.10	1.830±1.03	2.3779	0.0077
tetradecane	20.496	1400	1394.5	6.3343±2.72	25.32±11.1	2.2216	0.0093
decane, 1-iodo-	22.064	1433	1457.7	2.28±0.92	0.403±0.17	2.6789	0.0041
1-decanol, 2-hexyl-	22.902	1504	1490.7	n.d.	5.213±2.85	2.3017	0.0086
pentadecane	23.005	1500	1490.8	5.1290±3.32	24.77±16.8	1.4756	0.0395
tetradecanoic acid	29.116	1768	1768	5.9892±3.54	65.00±17.4	2.1756	0.0093
2-heptadecanone	31.738	1902	1897.6	25.581±9.07	n.d.	3.2112	0.0015
oleic acid	36.325	2141	2114.8	37.378±17.12	8.189±5.19	2.1854	0.0093
eicosanoic acid	40.607	2362	2321.8	19.557±10.83	n.d.	2.1665	0.0093
11-methyltricosane	41.071	2334	2343.4	3.9197±2.33	28.74±16.6	1.9617	0.0142
pentacosane	43.922	2500	2481	5.7387±2.00	515.7±9.10	13.651	0.0005
11-methylpentacosane	45.192	2535	2542.8	76.01±12.95	115.6±8.12	3.3865	0.0011

The list consists of only the compounds that were identified; NIST RI and the calculated RI (> 50 difference); RT=retention time; NIST RI=retention indices acquired from the National Institute of Standards and Technology database

(NIST); Calculated RI=retention indices calculated using n-alkane standard C7-C40; p values were generated by t-tests as (p≤0.05, n=5); n.d.=not detected. FDR is a false discovery rate of data.

Table 2. Significant Compounds Peak Area (One Unit Corresponds to a 10⁵ Area) Detected from Non-Infested and Adult *T. variabile* Infested Oats

Compounds	RT	NIST RI	Calculated RI	Non-infested	Infested	p value (10 ⁻³)	FDR
cis-3-methylcyclohexanol	8.327	964	895.4	16.34±4.71	29.83±5.20	2.578	0.0050
nonanal	12.043	1104	1063.4	6.30±4.02	69.58±18.47	4.1517	0.0002

decanal	15.185	1206	1202.6	n.d.	57.20±21.83	2.2005	0.0112
undecane, 2,6-dimethyl-	15.376	1210	1210.2	n.d.	52.51±24.51	2.0373	0.0143
pentadecane, 7-methyl-	16.808	1541	1258.4	4.47±1.06	2.755±1.03	1.4905	0.0384
dodecane, 2,6,11-trimethyl-	17.265	1275	1273.6	n.d.	17.97±4.69	4.1175	0.0002
tridecane	17.825	1300	1292.8	n.d.	595.8±26.01	9.9024	0.0003
tetradecane	20.496	1400	1394.5	0.67±0.12	4.248±2.83	1.6458	0.0282
1-decanol, 2-hexyl-	22.814	1504	1490.7	0.74±0.04	0.35±0.11	3.9916	0.0002
pentadecane	23.005	1500	1490.8	7.36±0.78	n.d.	6.9485	0.0007
hexadecane	25.363	1600	1592.3	3.20±1.91	n.d.	1.9806	0.0153
2-pentadecanone	25.686	1698	1607.7	4.00±3.50	72.74±11.60	5.8502	0.0007
2-heptenoic acid, 2-ethylhexyl ester	26.284	1678	1634.6	2.61±1.73	n.d.	1.8079	0.021
pentadecanal-	27.942	1715	1711.6	33.05±20.76	0.103±0.03	2.1229	0.0125
tetradecanoic acid	29.116	1768	1768	53.48±26.52	0.204±0.22	2.6937	0.0042
2-pentadecanone, 6,10,14-trimethyl-	30.14	1844	1817.5	n.d.	427.10±7.10	7.9105	0.0007
pentadecanoic acid	31.119	1867	1864.4	6.26±1.53	n.d.	4.3027	0.0002
2-heptadecanone	31.476	1902	1897.6	n.d.	3.59±2.46	1.7656	0.0225
n-hexadecanoic acid	33.097	1986	1958.1	11.00±12.08	68.31±18.93	3.3448	0.0010
octadecanoic acid	36.724	2172	2134.1	n.d.	7.814±2.50	3.6693	0.0005
eicosanoic acid	40.607	2362	2321.8	n.d.	430.47±11.76	7.5137	0.0002

The list consists of only the compounds that were identified; NIST RI and the calculated RI (> 50 difference); RT=retention time; NIST RI=retention indices acquired from National Institute of Standards and Technology database

(NIST); Calculated RI=retention indices calculated using n-alkane standard C7-C40; p values were generated by t-tests as ($p \leq 0.05$, $n=5$); ND=not detected. FDR is false discovery rate of data.

Table 3. Significant Compounds Peak Area (One Unit Corresponds to a 10^5 Area) Detected from Non-Infested and Adult *T. variabile* Infested Barley

Compound name	RT	NIST RI	Calculated RI	Non-infested	Infested	p value (10^{-3})	FDR
Nonanal	12.043	1104	1063.4	n.d.	16.90±7.71	2.5626	0.0070
Dodecane	14.953	1214	1193.7	65.94±13.11	24.81±7.52	3.5294	0.0015
Decanal	15.185	1206	1202.6	56.39±10.17	83.21±14.45	2.0243	0.0180
cyclopropane, nonyl-	16.151	1285	1235.7	3.81±0.70	45.59±31.44	1.7482	0.0226
dodecane, 2,6,11-trimethyl-	17.269	1275	1273.6	4.03±0.56	34.75±22.88	1.7691	0.0226
Tridecane	17.825	1300	1293	2.22±0.66	114.2±17.59	8.1822	0.0001
dodecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-	19.88	1366	1370.7	1.30±0.11	5.617±1.63	3.4427	0.0015
1-tetradecene	20.287	1392	1386.6	4.42±1.07	1.77±1.78	1.6628	0.0253
Tetradecane	20.495	1400	1394.5	63.24±15.61	1.43±0.43	2.5217	0.0070
Caryophyllene	21.073	1419	1416	5.69±3.77	0.66±0.40	1.7376	0.0226
2-tridecanone	22.954	1497	1489.1	63.87±19.38	1.03±0.24	2.3141	0.0101
Pentadecane	23.005	1500	1491	1.46±0.29	31.39±10.17	1.7515	0.0226
Hexadecane	23.358	1600	1592.3	18.94±8.19	2.06±1.07	2.7362	0.0055
2-pentadecanone	27.607	1698	1695.7	29.87±7.49	2.04±1.06	1.9047	0.0201

2-pentadecanone, 6,10,14-trimethyl-	30.14	1844	1842.9	2.986±0.69	0.68±0.67	3.1348	0.0025
2-heptadecanone	31.805	1902	1897.6	16.87±11.52	0.22±0.14	1.9188	0.0201
n-hexadecanoic acid	33.063	1986	1958.1	0.837±0.09	n.d.	6.8607	0.0001

The list consists of only the compounds that were identified; NIST RI and the calculated RI (> 50 difference); RT=retention time; NIST RI=retention indices acquired from the National Institute of Standards and Technology database (NIST); Calculated RI=retention indices calculated using n-alkane standard C7-C40; p values were generated by t-tests as ($p \leq 0.05$, $n=5$); ND=not detected. FDR is a false discovery rate of data.

Analysis and Identification of the Main Volatile Organic Compounds

The results indicated that the type of insect host grains significantly affected the volatile organic compounds emitted from both non-infested and infested wheat, oats, and barley. The number of emitted compounds varied slightly among different host grains, and the host grains also influenced the peak area of certain compounds.

The Principal Component Analyses (PCAs) demonstrated the impact of host type on both the quality and quantity of the chemical compounds (Figure 2a). The principal components (PCs) in the score plot illustrate the differentiation between the host grains (Figure 2b). The graph clearly shows distinct separation among all the diet types. However, the most pronounced differentiation in both female and male samples was observed between oats and the other grain types.

Significant differentiation in the VOCs produced between the different diet types was observed. For example, in wheat pentacosane; n-hexadecanoic acid; pentanoic acid; 11-methylpentacosane; tetradecane; decanal, and tridecane were emitted from wheat (Figure 2, a); 2-pentadecanone; dodecane; tridecane; decanal; undecane, 2,6-dimethyl- and eicosanoic acid were detected in oats (Figure 2b); and that from barley four main compounds decanoic acid, cyclopropane, nonyl-, tridecane and pentadecane were produced (Figure 2c). The loading plots show the most important compounds that

significantly participated in the differentiation among the diet types. These results show that pentacosane, n-hexadecanoic acid, pentanoic acid, 11-methylpentacosane, tetradecane, decanal, and tridecane were emitted from wheat (Figure 2a). While 2-pentadecanone, dodecane, tridecane, decanal, undecane, 2,6-dimethyl- and eicosanoic acid were detected in oats (Figure 2b). Results in Figure 2, c showed that four main compounds were identified that include including n-decanoic acid, cyclopropane, nonyl-, tridecane, and pentadecane.

Figure 2. Loading Plots Show the Most Significant Compounds that Participated in the Differentiation between Non-Infested and Infested Grains a: Wheat, b: Oats, c: Barley

There is considerable interest in detecting volatile compounds produced by insect feeding during the early stages of infestation in stored grain, as this can support timely pest management and prevent spoilage, ultimately reducing substantial economic losses for growers. The hypotheses of this study were confirmed: (a) volatile organic compounds (VOCs) produced by grain insects can be utilized for the early detection of insect infestations in stored grain, even before visible signs or symptoms appear, and (b) VOCs can be emitted from commodities after harvest and during storage, either directly from the grain or due to insect infestation. This study, therefore, confirmed the potential use of VOCs for early detection of *Trogoderma variabile* in grain storage facilities.

The results of this study confirm the hypothesis that VOCs can be used to determine the presence of *T. variabile* in storage facilities at an early stage of development. However, some of the compounds were detected or increased after infestation. This could be due to infestation of *T. variabile*. Some of the compounds were identified from *Tribolium castanum* and *Rhyzopertha dominica*. Previous studies such as dodecane; nonanal; decanal; 1-tetradecene; dodecanal; and pentadecane (Alnajim et al., 2019; Alnajim 2020; Niu et al. 2016). Niu et al. (2016) reported that nonanal, decanal, dodecane, tridecane, dodecanal, 1-tetradecene, and pentadecane were identified from the floor and floor infested with *Tribolium castanum*. Also, these results containing many compounds were similar to those reported previously in wheat flour and whole-wheat grains (Seitz, 1995; Maeda et al., 2008) and to those identified in sorghum or corn (Seitz et al., 1999, Buttery et al., 1995), such as dodecane, nonanal, tridecane, and tetradecane. Seitz (1995) found several compounds from samples of wheat infested by *R. dominica*, but these were not detected in the present study. This could be since a different method and different collection temperature (28°C) was used compared to the current study. This could be because different varieties of grains produce different volatiles. Also, some compounds have been identified from healthy

wheat flour, including dodecane, tridecane, nonanal, tetradecane, and oleic acid. Moreover, n-hexadecanoic acid has already been recorded as an aggregation cue for the females of the Khapra beetle, *Trogoderma granarium* Everts (Coleoptera: Dermestidae), and also this compound was used as an indicator of the presence of this species (Cohen et al., 1971). Some other compounds were detected from non-infested and infested rice with different coleoptera insects that include nonanal; dodecane; decanal; tridecane; 1-tetradecene; tetradecane; pentadecane; hexadecane and n-hexadecanoic acid.

Conclusion

It is evident that a variety of volatile organic compounds are produced by insects during the colonization of wheat grain. Some of these compounds could serve as valuable indicators for the early detection of grain infestation. Previous studies suggest that monitoring VOCs may provide an effective early warning of both quality degradation and infestation. As such, there is a pressing need for early and efficient methods to detect infested grain and distinguish between harmful and harmless species. For the grain industry, a key priority should be assessing the presence of molds in Australian grains produced under different conditions to better identify when insect species are active. Developing modern, fast, and user-friendly tools to identify infestations at early stages could help prevent significant losses and the downgrading of grain quality.

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